

Screening (partial report)

Update of:

Educational interventions to improve people's understanding of key concepts in assessing the effects of health interventions

Executive summary

This is the partial report of the search screening for the update of the systematic review of educational interventions designed to improve people's understanding of key concepts for evaluating claims about the effects of health interventions.

We performed a comprehensive search in CENTRAL, EMBASE, MEDLINE and Epistemonikos database from January 2015 up to 20 December 2022.

Only three articles were identified. These were additional references of trials included in the original version of the review.

Inclusion criteria

Type of evidence	(for the partial report): Randomised trials.
Population	<p>All types of study participants (learners) were eligible except university students undertaking a health professional degree and health professionals.</p> <p>Health students and/or health professionals were excluded from the review, as an educational intervention provided to them on this topic is most likely designed to assist them to perform decision-making with their patients, rather than decision-making regarding their own health.</p>
Intervention	<p>Any article evaluating an educational intervention aimed to help the participants (learners) understand one or more of the key concepts considered relevant to evaluating the effects of health interventions and/or the interpretation of research results, as long as the examples/scenarios used were within the context of health information or claims, health conditions, the human body and/or conventional, complementary or alternative healthcare treatments.</p> <p>Some examples are: educational interventions related to evidence-based skills, the evidence-based process, scientific reasoning, critical health literacy skills, basic research concepts, randomized trial concepts, assessing claims about health treatments and specific topics such as randomisation, blinding, causation, placebo, statistical reasoning and understanding risk. Interventions designed to improve informed consent about participating in a specific clinical trial are not eligible.</p>

Methods

This is an update of a systematic review of educational interventions designed to improve people's understanding of key concepts for evaluating claims about the effects of health interventions (1).

Electronic searches

We conduct searches in Epistemonikos, Pubmed/MEDLINE, EMBASE and CENTRAL from January 2015 up to 20 December 2022. We did not apply language or publication status restrictions (Databases CINAHL, ERIC y Critical thinking and Appraisal Resource Library are pending).

Selection of the studies

The results from the electronic searches were uploaded to Collaboratron, the screening tool of the L:OVE (Living Overview of Evidence) classification platform. The records from the searches in each individual source were de-duplicated by an algorithm that compares unique identifiers (database ID, DOI, trial registry ID), and citation details (i.e. author names, journal, year of publication, volume, number, pages, article title, and article abstract).

Considering the large volume of articles, we used a previously validated artificial intelligence classifier in order to exclude articles with a low probability of being a primary study.

Title and abstract screening was performed independently by two reviewers, and a third review author resolved any disagreement. We obtained the full text for all titles that appeared to meet the inclusion criteria or required further analysis. They were assessed independently by two reviewers, and discrepancies were resolved by a third reviewer. We recorded the reasons for excluding articles at the full text stage and outlined the study selection process in a PRISMA flow diagram, which we adapted for the purpose of this review. Excluded articles are reported in Appendix 2.

- (1) Cusack, L., Del Mar, C. B., Chalmers, I., Gibson, E., & Hoffmann, T. C. (2018). Educational interventions to improve people's understanding of key concepts in assessing the effects of health interventions: a systematic review. *Systematic reviews*, 7(1), 68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-018-0719-4>
- (2) Andres Carvallo, Denis Parra, Gabriel Rada, Daniel Perez, Juan Ignacio Vasquez, Camilo Vergara (2020). Neural language models for text classification in evidence-based medicine. arXiv preprint . <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2012.00584>

Results:

From 43,692 records identified from the electronic searches, 7,737 records were available to screen after the removal of duplicates and the exclusion of references by the artificial intelligence classifier. We considered 26 of them as potentially eligible and obtained and evaluated their full texts. Finally, three articles were included. These corresponded to additional reports of trials identified in the original version of the review. (see PRISMA flowchart in appendix 1).

List of included references

Study	Reference
IHC Primary Schools	Nsangi A, Semakula D, Oxman AD, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Oxman M, Rosenbaum S, Morelli A, Glenton C, Lewin S, Kaseje M, Chalmers I, Fretheim A, Ding Y, Sewankambo NK. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects, 1-year follow-up: a cluster-randomised trial. <i>Trials</i> . 2020;21(1):27. (d56d88306fc3812fe5cbda3a4b0c651b363e97fb).
	Nsangi, Allen. Effects of the Informed Health Choices primary school intervention on the ability of children in Uganda to assess the reliability of claims about treatment effects, a cluster-randomised trial. <i>Canadian Conference on Global Health</i> . 2019; (9ad95935bb4c4a08568118b350245c24e344ced8)
IHC Podcast Trial	Semakula D, Nsangi A, Oxman AD, Oxman M, Austvoll-Dahlgren A, Rosenbaum S, Morelli A, Glenton C, Lewin S, Nyirazinyoye L, Kaseje M, Chalmers I, Fretheim A, Rose CJ, Sewankambo NK. Effects of the Informed Health Choices podcast on the ability of parents of primary school children in Uganda to assess the trustworthiness of claims about treatment effects: one-year follow up of a randomised trial. <i>Trials</i> . 2020;21(1):187. (7c0268af2b40c538a295db1a8cf52d97c1392a4b)

Appendix 1. Adapted PRISMA flowchart

Appendix 2. List of excluded references

Reference	Reason for exclusion
Davies C, McGillion M, Rowland C, Matthews D. Can inferencing be trained in preschoolers using shared book-reading? A randomised controlled trial of parents' inference-eliciting questions on oral inferencing ability. <i>Journal of child language</i> . 2020;47(3):655-679. [5cf4423b486b42cd1b154fa7c684e6aa40124ca3]	Not about key concepts
El Miedany, Y, El Gaafary, M, Lotfy, H, El Aroussy, N, Mekkawy, D, Nasef, SI, Farag, Y, Almedany, S, Wassif, G, PRINTO, Egypt. Shared decision-making aid for juvenile idiopathic arthritis: moving from informative patient education to interactive critical thinking. <i>Clinical rheumatology</i> . 2019;38(11):3217-3225. [33ff4078b38fe6ba1ec27ce89aa1feb8cd00d7fe]	Not about key concepts
Elsharkawy NB, Abdelaziz EM, Ouda MM, Oraby FA. Effectiveness of Health Information Package Program on Knowledge and Compliance among Pregnant Women with Anemia: A Randomized Controlled Trial. <i>International journal of environmental research and public health</i> . 2022;19(5). [ed91c7e21efa252aa90cfd0602f8d92651259e1b]	Not about key concepts
Golembiewski EH, Mainous AG, Rahmanian KP, Brumback B, Rooks BJ, Krieger JL, Goodman KW, Moseley RE, Harle CA. An Electronic Tool to Support Patient-Centered Broad Consent: A Multi-Arm Randomized Clinical Trial in Family Medicine. <i>Annals of family medicine</i> . 2021;19(1):16-23. [f2cab199a7f2d977eacd74247754a506d2cd7a2d]	Not about key concepts
Housten AJ, Kamath GR, Bevers TB, Cantor SB, Dixon N, Hite A, Kallen MA, Leal VB, Li L, Volk RJ. Does Animation Improve Comprehension of Risk Information in Patients with Low Health Literacy? A Randomized Trial. <i>Medical decision making : an international journal of the Society for Medical Decision Making</i> . 2020;40(1):17-28. [175aea0abfb881fdd10f1c1cabde8ecaee371807]	Not about key concepts
Imms C, Novak I, Kerr C, Shields N, Randall M, Harvey A, Graham HK, Reddihough D. Improving allied health professionals' research implementation behaviours for children with cerebral palsy: protocol for a before-after study. <i>Implementation science : IS</i> . 2015;10:16. [c532764c128bea635d41fa91abec2b1d62ec8318]	Not about key concepts
Isselhard A, Töpper M, Berger-Höger B, Steckelberg A, Fischer H, Vitinius F, Beifus K, Köberlein-Neu J, Wiedemann R, Rhiem K, Schmutzler R, Stock S. Implementation and evaluation of a nurse-led decision-coaching program for healthy breast cancer susceptibility gene (BRCA1/2) mutation carriers: a study protocol for the randomized controlled EDCP-BRCA study. <i>Trials</i> . 2020;21(1):501. [9cab08c0a2d3e3282b0ca13327d5f35e6f1d9c8b]	Not about key concepts
Itoh N, Mishima H, Yoshida Y, Yoshida M, Oka H, Matsudaira K. Evaluation of the Effect of Patient Education and Strengthening Exercise Therapy Using a Mobile Messaging App on Work Productivity in Japanese Patients With Chronic Low Back Pain: Open-Label, Randomized, Parallel-Group Trial. <i>JMIR</i>	Not about key concepts

mHealth and uHealth. 2022;10(5):e35867. [df6a75438efead41f5fd9263dcb2e2e55dd84526]	
Kludas L, Kriston L, Metzner F, Wichmann M, Pawils S. [Effects of written educational material on parental health knowledge depending on socioeconomic status : A randomized controlled trial]. Bundesgesundheitsblatt, Gesundheitsforschung, Gesundheitsschutz. 2018;61(4):385-393. [e8df4df800eaa8db2b9c35e495ad1baf0567e97]	Not about key concepts
Linn, AJ, van Dijk, L, van Weert, JCM, Gebeyehu, BG, van Bodegraven, AA, Smit, EG. Creating a synergy effect: a cluster randomized controlled trial testing the effect of a tailored multimedia intervention on patient outcomes. Patient education and counseling. 2018;101(8):1419-1426. [9367d5a8a7357d436543b724abd17f7ed6084ca1]	Not about key concepts
McCaffery KJ, Morony S, Muscat DM, Smith SK, Shepherd HL, Dhillon HM, Hayen A, Luxford K, Meshreky W, Comings J, Nutbeam D. Evaluation of an Australian health literacy training program for socially disadvantaged adults attending basic education classes: study protocol for a cluster randomised controlled trial. BMC public health. 2016;16:454. [e484555375c5ced9851d429db58c396990bd94fb]	Not about key concepts
McElfish PA, Purvis RS, Scott AJ, Haggard-Duff LK, Riklon S, Long CR. "The results are encouragements to make positive changes to be healthier:" qualitative evaluation of Marshallese participants' perceptions when receiving study results in a randomized control trial. Contemporary clinical trials communications. 2020;17:100543. [0b7605a7be7d6090b82113f177242b2af877fe24]	Not about key concepts
Morony S, Lamph E, Muscat D, Nutbeam D, Dhillon HM, Shepherd H, Smith S, Khan A, Osborne J, Meshreky W, Luxford K, Hayen A, McCaffery KJ. Improving health literacy through adult basic education in Australia. Health promotion international. 2018;33(5):867-877. [cfb1a5bd834940a20e73c8924c7eb5112255aa73]	Not about key concepts
Politi MC, Kuzemchak MD, Kaphingst KA, Perkins H, Liu J, Byrne MM. Decision Aids Can Support Cancer Clinical Trials Decisions: Results of a Randomized Trial. The oncologist. 2016;21(12):1461-1470. [c1a0ff55a0fe5db8cef626f433a438e602932f12]	Not about key concepts
Rahn, AC, Backhus, I, Fuest, F, Riemann-Lorenz, K, Köpke, S, van de Roemer, A, Mühlhauser, I, Heesen, C. Comprehension of confidence intervals - development and piloting of patient information materials for people with multiple sclerosis: qualitative study and pilot randomised controlled trial. BMC medical informatics and decision making. 2016;16(1):122. [57e1d53c6c52d72180ca7bc6461849a71c65eb9d]	Not about key concepts
Schiefer J, Golle J, Tibus M, Herbein E, Gindele V, Trautwein U, Oschatz K. Effects of an extracurricular science intervention on elementary school children's epistemic beliefs: A randomized controlled trial. The British journal of educational psychology. 2020;90(2):382-402. [a8ec311cf200f4a0c1df534d51e2418376f3e4fe]	Not about key concepts

<p>Shinde S, Weiss HA, Khandeparkar P, Pereira B, Sharma A, Gupta R, Ross DA, Patton G, Patel V. A multicomponent secondary school health promotion intervention and adolescent health: An extension of the SEHER cluster randomised controlled trial in Bihar, India. <i>PLoS medicine</i>. 2020;17(2):e1003021. [7ea680c54020d8b4deb4ddc41966583dbfc10103]</p>	Not about key concepts
<p>Smith CA, Chang E, Gallego G, Khan A, Armour M, Balneaves LG. An education intervention to improve decision making and health literacy among older Australians: a randomised controlled trial. <i>BMC geriatrics</i>. 2019;19(1):129. [887a3651a165adcb8a66bb717fc293bba6a17a6f]</p>	Not about key concepts
<p>Thompson CA, Taber JM, Sidney PG, Fitzsimmons CJ, Mielicki MK, Matthews PG, Schemmel EA, Simonovic N, Foust JL, Aurora P, Disabato DJ, Seah THS, Schiller LK, Coifman KG. Math matters: A novel, brief educational intervention decreases whole number bias when reasoning about COVID-19. <i>Journal of experimental psychology. Applied</i>. 2021;27(4):632-656. [31e1371b0f6dc005392bae871c8e52caa11d2feb]</p>	Not about key concepts
<p>Trost SG, Byrne R, Williams KE, Johnson BJ, Bird A, Simon K, Chai LK, Terranova CO, Christian HE, Golley RK. Study protocol for Healthy Conversations @ Playgroup: a multi-site cluster randomized controlled trial of an intervention to promote healthy lifestyle behaviours in young children attending community playgroups. <i>BMC public health</i>. 2021;21(1):1757. [1f2ac0463ec4b85f374f948ea8c4f4e931c0c42a]</p>	Not about key concepts
<p>Waters EA, Maki J, Liu Y, Ackermann N, Carter CR, Dart H, Bowen DJ, Cameron LD, Colditz GA. Risk Ladder, Table, or Bulleted List? Identifying Formats That Effectively Communicate Personalized Risk and Risk Reduction Information for Multiple Diseases. <i>Medical decision making : an international journal of the Society for Medical Decision Making</i>. 2021;41(1):74-88. [e77d5afe5251fb54e93ac3ffe7b9f979abe86e3e]</p>	Not about key concepts
<p>Wenke RJ, Thomas R, Hughes I, Mickan S. The effectiveness and feasibility of TREAT (Tailoring Research Evidence and Theory) journal clubs in allied health: a randomised controlled trial. <i>BMC medical education</i>. 2018;18(1):104. [253d27f3a16f6c86d0a2046ebd7edf201a5464f7]</p>	No lay people
<p>Zinn S, Landrock U, Gnamb T. Web-based and mixed-mode cognitive large-scale assessments in higher education: An evaluation of selection bias, measurement bias, and prediction bias. <i>Behavior research methods</i>. 2021;53(3):1202-1217. [a87c28fddef95c8c408cae04f0c1c4a470ae7cf5]</p>	Not about key concepts